

Participation of the Forest Research Institute in conference INFOBAZY 2017

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The 8th INFOBAZY conference, under the auspices of the IT Committee of the Polish Academy of Sciences, the Ministry of Science and Higher Education and the Gdansk University of Technology, was held under the motto ‘data, knowledge, e-services’ (Fig. 1). The idea of the conference organized traditionally by the Academic Computer Centre TASK network, the Institute of Oceanology of the Polish Academy of Sciences and the Faculty of Electronics, Telecommunications and Informatics of the Gdansk University of Technology is the integration of scientific community around the scientific issues of databases, data processing and the sharing and use of scientific data by scientific institutions and administration. For years, the conference has been promoting Polish science and its integration with the European research area.

This year’s theme of the presented papers related to open access to data and scientific knowledge, methods of extracting knowledge from large data sets (Big Data) and its use in various types of networks and information systems. The conference program included 6 scientific sessions:

1. The development of digital libraries
2. Open Access to university scientific research
3. Big Data for medical applications
4. Big Data in the natural sciences
5. Cloud computing management
6. Data mining for maritime economy.

The plenary papers highlighted the rapid development of information technology on a global scale, and

Figure 1. The Gdansk University of Technology

Source: conference materials

showed the impact of new technologies on the directions of research in many scientific fields. Modern research infrastructure and computing technology allow you to collect, process, analyse more and more data sets. Research funding organizations and renowned

scientific journals are increasingly putting demands on open access to data, repeatability of laboratory tests, including computer simulations. The condition conducted research from public funds ensure adequate standards of scientific data storage and allow open access. During the conference, the principles of operation of the repository *DataPort*, which was established on the initiative of IIEEE, were presented. The new repository works in global scale and it allows to store both raw data, analytical tools, and analysis results. Each object stored in *DataPort* receives a DOI that can be cited, just as with traditional publications. Discussion on the development of the information society was initiated during the second scientific session. Digital society, through the knowledge society becomes a society of wisdom that, through ever greater and faster access to information, is able to solve the challenges of civilization. Whereas, in the presentation of scientific information system, OMEGA PSIR (Warsaw University of Technology) presented the principles of construction of the profile of scientists based on the whole of their activities, and not just in terms of their scientific publications. The implemented new technological solutions, according to the authors of

the system, increase the attractiveness and readability of the scientific information.

The issue of access to research results of the Forest Research Institute (IBL) was presented in the scientific session 'Big Data in the natural sciences'. The first presentation 'Searching for appropriate scientific communication patterns for forest research in Poland' concerned the issue of open access to specialist bibliographic information on forest studies and the role of domain repositories in modern information systems. In the second presentation, 'Open access to research data on forest ecosystems in Poland', attention has been paid to a significant increase of data resources, especially spatial data, in the context of use of modern measurement and calculation technology in forest research. Ways to share scientific data of the IBL (scientific publications, information systems, scientific portals, licenses to use the data) were also presented. In the final part of the presentation, problems related to access to raw data in terms of legal regulations and data management in scientific units were presented. More information about the conference is available at <http://infobazy.gda.pl>.